

TRENDS IN THE SPREAD OF EXTREMIST IDEAS AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE (USING THE EXAMPLE OF SOCIAL NETWORKS).

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The development of our country as a result of the large-scale domestic and foreign policy pursued in our country in today's rapidly developing time, not seeing progress in various fields, in particular, progress in the religious and educational sphere, avoiding punishment for their extremist and terrorist actions and promoting radical Islamic ideas under the guise of "religious ulema" from the outside, These may include Rashod Kamolov and Zofir Gafforov.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev stated at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly in September 2017 that "the growing presence of terrorist taxidermists in the world, especially in recent years, is a sign that the methods of combating them, mainly with the use of force, are not justified." "Ultrasound". In this regard, Cup is not limited to the main causes of taxidermy in Hals, but only if you know how to deal with their consequences. The root of international terrorism and extremism, along with other factors, are envy and intolerance." In this regard, people, first of all, stated that the formation and education of the mind and thinking of young people on the basis of education is the most important task.

In the case of the subject under study, which lists the terms used in the legislation, we can include the following in them.

Extremism is an expression of extreme forms of actions aimed at destabilizing the socio-political situation, forcibly consolidating the constitutional system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, forcibly occupying the Republic of Uzbekistan and depriving it of power, inciting national, racial, ethnic or religious hatred[1].

Terrorism – in order to achieve political, religious, ideological and other goals, to compel a State, an international organization, an individual or a legal entity to commit or refrain from committing any actions, complicate international relations, violate the sovereignty, divine integrity of the State, undermine its security, commit shameful actions in resolving the issue of armed conflicts, to, The Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for the

use of violence aimed at destabilizing the socio-political situation, rape or other criminal acts[2].

Today, comprehensive work is being carried out in our country to comprehensively support young people, achieve their goals and ensure harmonious human growth, including every year

It is advisable to mention that on June 30, the celebration of "Youth Day" in our country as a holiday resulted in a road trip, stating that youth policy is above all.

In the current vaccine, spiritual taxidermies of various shapes and guises are mainly aimed at the younger generation, and the main reason is that young people are the most active stratum of society, they are most likely to be in demand due to their addiction to various Goya influences. At the same time, the enjoyment of youth consciousness is determined by the fact that Khar Kandai is of strategic importance for ideological power, the prospects of the country, confidence in the future are determined precisely by etiquette, the interests of young people and the goals that follow from them. That's why Ham is winning the hearts and minds of our youth today, realizing the importance of sorting information, increasing immunity and the ability to distinguish white from black.

It should be noted that, according to our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "educating youth means educating the people," now under this slogan our youth closely connects the fate of Uzbekistan with the new Uzbekistan. The new Uzbekistan lives in a state of pride in the achievements of the whole society, the appearance of the cities and villages of our country is undeniably changing, production and industry are developing rapidly, its composition is radically being updated[3].

These updates and changes give our youth even more strength and support. Our young people are deeply aware that opportunities and conditions have been created among their peers in the world, which are no less than anyone else's.

Our President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, speaking at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly on September 19, 2017, addressed the peoples of the world on the following extremely topical issues:

- A) The growing threat of terrorism in the world, especially in recent years.
- B) that the fight against terrorism is conducted mainly through the use of force, and this method of struggle does not justify itself.
- C) so that it is not limited to the main causes, which in many cases create threats, but only allows you to deal with their consequences.

(G) Identifying the roots of international terrorism and extremism, along with other factors such as exclusion and intolerance.

D) the fact that people, first of all, form and educate the mind and thinking of young people on the basis of education is the most important task.

E) extremist activity and propensity to violence due to the fact that most crimes are committed by young people under the age of 30.

K) the modern youth in the world is the most numerous generation in the history of all mankind, its number is 2 billion people.

H) the next day of our planet, the fact that its well-being is related to how much our children grow up as human beings.

I) Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to show their potential, to prevent the spread of the "virus" of the idea of violence. [4].

It follows from the above that the role of the youth of our country in the eyes of society and the state is increasing, increasing the maximum and level of tasks that are set before society and the state in educational work carried out among young people, in the formation of immunity against destructive ideological attitudes. it affects their consciousness, taking into account their socio-demographic, psychophysiological characteristics, it is necessary to recognize with joy that a fair domestic and foreign policy conducted under the general leadership of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev during the period of new reforms and development of our country ensures peace and stability in our country thanks to strong will, determination, tolerance, navigation our people.

Recent terrorist attacks around the world are not being carried out against government agencies, harbors, law enforcement agencies or enemy facilities, but in connection with attacks on natural and man-made States, including large enterprises and organizations, and the fact that young people make up the majority of those who commit terrorist acts in the form of fires or mass poisoning This can be called the reason that young people feel insecure and do not understand the consequences of their behavior.

Today, we can observe that Internet social networks, carried out by the ideological leaders of destructive extremist and terrorist organizations around the world, are actively recruiting in order to significantly strengthen the processes of Islamization and radicalization among the population aged 18 to 30 years in certain Central Asian states. by doing the following work to achieve your goals.

- Incitement of national, interethnic, ethnic and religious hatred.

- To carry out ideological work with citizens directly and remotely (via the Internet).
- Creating a positive image of a terrorist.
- Material interest.
- The formation of distrust of the state by exaggerating the secondary social problems of the country.
- Promotion of the norms of Islam and Sharia, which are commented on by themselves [5].

When we theoretically and practically studied how our youth, the future of our country, falls under the influence of extremist and terrorist organizations and movements, it was noticed that the following factors directly contribute.

- the diligence of the self-governing bodies of the citizens of God in carrying out their official tasks and the inability to establish cooperation with relevant organizations.

- Parents' lack of control.
- Dysfunctional families.
- Harmful consequences of inefficient use of the Internet.
- External migration.
- Low quality of education in educational institutions.
- Abstinence from alcohol consumption.
- Getting under the influence of narcotic and psychotropic substances.
- Mass culture.
- Negligence of organizations that are directly responsible for the education of young people.
- The inability to attract a wide audience of young people through religious educational channels and groups engaged in spiritual and educational activities on social networks.

- The fact that representatives of the official religious sphere do not have a proper reputation among young people does not allow them to fully convey religious concepts to young people.

- This is suitable for Maksad if we point out a number of reasons, such as the fact that pro-Armenian persons acting through social networks are not limited to conducting propaganda work, that is, they are not subject to prohibitions.

For this reason, in accordance with the Maccsad, we are taking the following measures to prevent young people from falling under the influence of extremist and terrorist organizations and streams, as indicated above.

- Formation of lists of citizens to improve the work of self-government bodies, to determine what activities young people living in makhallas are engaged in.

- Formation of a correct and sympathetic attitude among young people towards extremist and terrorist ideas and destructive influences.

-To improve the modern knowledge of young people, including - to adapt to phenomena, to form skills not to lose heart.

- Timely elimination of problems that arise when our citizens receive information relevant to the interests of society and the state through social networks.

- It is necessary to implement measures to strengthen the promotion of pure concepts of the Islamic religion through social contacts, which are rapidly gaining popularity among our youth.

- To strengthen the effectiveness of the fight against the spread of ideas, and not with the appearance of signs of the spread of extremist and terrorist ideas among our youth.

The influence of destructive ideas on the consciousness of young people as a result of surveys conducted in 2021, mainly in order to find out whether kaysi comes from sources, 85% of respondents answered "The Internet", 12% - from street acquaintances, 3% - from others. Self-destructive ideas affecting the consciousness of young people today, the Internet with the advent of orcali, the role of the Internet among modern youth has increased significantly, an important task today is to focus on developing work in this direction in order to minimize their exposure to destructive ideas due to the fact that they join to find like-minded people.

Article 9 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Youth Policy" dated September 14, 2016 defines the state bodies implementing State youth policy as:

- State educational management bodies and educational institutions;
- state bodies governing the health care system and medical and preventive institutions;
- bodies for physical culture and sports;
- cultural authorities;
- labor authorities;
- The Prosecutor's Office;
- internal affairs agencies;
- judicial authorities;

- defense agencies.

For this reason, it is advisable today to work in cooperation with the future of our country in order to prevent young people from getting lost in the ranks of extremist and terrorist movements and organizations by destructive forces of various manifestations.

In conclusion, I would like to say that at the present time, impregnating our youth with a deeply ideologized worldview, preventing them from falling under the influence of destructive forces of various manifestations, and forming the qualities of patriotism, justice, decency, and valor among young people is a requirement of today's era.

References:

1. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On countering extremism" dated July 30, 2018. Article
2. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On combating terrorism" dated December 15, 2000. Article 2.
3. (49) Bulletin of the Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2021.
4. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev from his speech at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly on September 19, 2017.
5. Methodological manual of the Ministry of Youth Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Prevention of falling under the influence of extremist ideas" - Tashkent-2019.
6. Methodical manual of the Ministry of Youth Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Prevention of clashes of youth under the influence of extremist movements" - Tashkent-2019.
7. Muhammad Amin Yaksia "Chemistry from shahids on the Internet": auxiliary educational material. Tashkent-2016.

